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IMPLEMENTATION OF CLUSTER BASED ROUTING FOR LIFETIME ENHANCEMENT IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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Abstract:

In the Wireless Sensor Networks system, data base transmission is constrained by limited battery energy for the nodes. The densely with deployed sensor nodes will get detected redundant and correlated data which can cause wastage of the energy. In order to save valuable resources and energy and in order to enhance the network's life-time, clustering oriented technique can be applied. In the cluster based networking, the cluster head to perform data aggregation and suitable routing. This research oriented project proposes a cluster based particular routing method with a power-saving system for enhancing the life-time. The overlapped coverage area of the randomly deployed nodules forms the basis of the power savvy schemes.

Keywords: Database; Energy; networking; overlapped; Wireless.

Introduction:-

The Wireless re-programming of a basic sensor network is much useful for updating new codes or for interchanging the functionality of existing program code. The reprogramming may be completed multiple times during a nodule's lifetime and therefore a nodule has to be remain receptive to the futuristic code updates. Conventional reprogramming protocol which includes Deluge and to achieve this by bundling the reprogramming protocols and their applications as one code image which is get transferred through the Wireless network.

Wireless associated Sensor Network eventually consisting of very large numbers of wireless nodes, which called sensor nodes and one or many more base stations must use as a sink. These sensor nodes used to collect information from the environment based on their sensing related mechanisms. The nodes deployed in very vast numbers collaborate to form an ad-

hoc networking capable of reporting to the data collection sink (i.e. base station). The wireless sensor network must have various applications such as habitat monitoring, building monitoring, health based monitoring and targeted tracking.

I. IMPORTANCE OF CLUSTERING TECHNIQUES

The most important issues regarding the Wireless Sensor Network is the limited battery power of the nodes. In most of their basic application sensors nodes must be deployed in harsh environments. This makes the recharging of these batteries most inconvenient or sometimes impossible. The Sensor nodes consume most of their limited battery energy to send and receive the data packets to equip the functions of its target applications. These resource constrained natures of sensor nodes is a major challenge to the design of WSNs. Therefore, there is a need to study alternative or new technologies which enable more effective use of scarce resources at individual sensor nodes for an application. Clustering is a very effective way to minimize the energy consumption. Objective of clustering is to reduce the total transmission power aggregated over the nodes in the pre-selective path, and to balance the loads among the nodes for prolonging the network lifetime. The sensor nodes may be organized into clusters and each cluster is managed by a special node or leader, called cluster head (CH). This (CH) is responsible for coordinating the data transaction activities of all the sensors in its cluster. Transaction to the base station is also performed by the (CH).

Fig: Basic Cluster Layout

The (CH) based node selection is one of its important issues in the clustering based techniques. Since every data transmission management scheme is performed by the head nodes, this nodes shall have sufficient amount of energy. Also since these energy of the (CH) depletes much faster than other nodes, there shall be some technique to rearrange the exhausted head with a new node.

This research paper finds out the techniques that associated with routing and the data transmissions in WSN which gets energy efficiency and prolonged life-time. The main contribution of that paper is the basic proposal of an energy efficient clustering based rout schemes with power saving mechanisms using the sleep and active schedules. The rest of this research initiative is organized as follows. An brief overview of the related work is described in section II. The proposed methodology is explained in the section III. Section IV presented the performance based evaluation and section V concludes the research presentation.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Numerous clustering based algorithms have been proposed for some ad-hoc and sensor based networks recently. The LEACH, is of the renowned application-specific algorithms that utilizes clustering to prolong the network's lifetime. In LEACH, the nodes organizes themselves into the very local clusters, with one of the node acting as the cluster's head. LEACH utilizes a probabilistic functionality for selecting the cluster's head which get ensures each node with a cluster's head roles.

In the Energy-Efficient Clustering Based Data Aggregation, ECBDA, first node is must be selected as a (CH) by utilizing its residual energy and that's specific communication cost factor. If the residual based energy is less than the required threshold value added system, a new clustering head is elected from the same clusters.

In the case of Hierarchical Flow Balancing Technique, it has the route construction phase system, in which the specific sensors are grouped into some clusters based on their overlapping degrees and then the hierarchical backbone networks is being constructed using the very clustering heads with the sink at the apex. In the data transmission related phases, the sensor

transmit the sensed data base to their clustering heads and then the heads get forwarded the data to the sink.

Jiguo et. al. proposed particular cluster-based routing protocol for the wireless sensors networking with non-uniform node distribution which get included an energy aware clustering algorithm such as EADC and a cluster based routing algorithm.

Clusters of equal sizes are formed and the relative energy consumption among clustering members can be balanced well. Another method called ERP-SCDS uses architecture with some static clusters to reduce the energy in the clustering process. To have energy efficient clustering based mechanism and well-distributed clustering, the initializations of static based clusters is handled by the sinking. The multi hoping routine discovery algorithm is get replaced by the relay node selection mechanism to further achieve better energy efficiency based Units.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research initiative mainly deals with the preservations of energy for particular cluster nodes. The overlapping based coverage area of the nodes remain the basis of this power saving schemes.

3.1 Cluster Formulation:

The initiation of cluster formulation phases is based on the static clustering methodology. Particular Sink collects the node positioning information from all the sensor nodes. According to coordinated positions which collected by the sink, the nodes must provided with an identity. During the cluster formulation, nodes with same of the identification will join the same cluster.

3.2. Head Election

\ The head election phases are based on the timer mechanism initially. Every node broadcasted on head advertisement messages to its neighbors. The initial timed-out node becomes the heading arch. The (CH) for the next round of the operation is get selected in the current round in itself. A reference value settled for residual energy of the head nodes, that value determines whether the head should get replaced or not at all. Furthermore head selection is depending upon average values of the residual energy. From the member nodes of exhausted head, the one with the highest residual energy is get selected as next head.

3.3. Route Discovery Process

This essential process involves the selection and identification of proper routing nodes. Each of the utilized cluster head transmits the data collected from its member nodes to the base station using these very routing nodes. The routing node selection is directly dependent on residual energy and its distance of parameters. The basic neighboring cluster heads interchange their energy related information with each other.

When any particular cluster head has the data to send it selects from its neighbors, the one with peak energy value as its next hope. Also the far from this node to the base station should be much lesser than that from the sending cluster head node.

3.4. Power Saving Scheduling

For transmitting and receiving data to the base station, the cluster members shall first transmit the dataset to respective cluster head. The particular data transmission is the most energy consuming task in the operation of basic WSN. So if the numbers of transmissions is get reduced, it saves a much considerable amount of essential energy.

During this research, the power saving is finally achieved using a sleep and pro active scheduling of the member nodes in each of the cluster. For this much randomly deployed node positions are considered into it. The sensors are deployed randomly to get the dataset transmitted. This particular phenomenon causes the coverage overlapping of the nodes.

The nodes are get itself driven to a sleeping state at which they finally get consumed only a limited amount of energy. This sleeping state of noes are based on two conditions

i) If greater than one of the node is deployed such that they get covered the same area, then only one that node is kept active and others are transmitted to sleeping state.

2) The overlapping coverage for all of the nodes are calculated. The nodes with the highest overlap are made to sleep.

The very first condition is used to be based on the fact that the random deployment causes the nodes to be so closer to each other and so they will have be the very same area of coverage. So developing one active node must preserve the energy of other nodes.

But for the second conditions, the overlapping coverage is get calculated initially. Here is the node within the transmission ranges of a particular nodes are called the neighbors of that node. A node whose overall coverage area is get overlapping with all its neighbors will have to be having the highest overlapping probability. Such a node is made to get into sleep state because of the initial interference caused by the overlapping process.

The position related information get passed by the members to their respective (CH) along with its residual energy parameters. Hence the cluster head to determine which of its members should be in sleeping state. When the cluster energy level of are below the predetermined threshold, the sleeping nodes are get active and the whole sleeping procedure get applied to the rest of the nodules. This process will get prolong the lifetime considerably as according to the scheduling, it is not to be repeated at each round but only when fifty percentages of nodes are below the energy constraint.

3.5. The State of Data Transmission

The nodes in the active state of transmission will have to transmit dataset to their respective clustering heads. For this reason the (CH) assigns the basic and most particular TDMA slots to each of the members. Every member must allowed to transmission during its own slot. The data received by the (CH) is remain aggregated and get forwarded to the corresponding routing node.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The observed method is simulated in required software. The experiment consists of (100.00) nodes that deployed randomly in an area of approximately (100m x 100meter) and all the nodes were given to the equal initial energy.

The operation gets first initiation by the sinking. Also the nodes are must assumed to be a location aware by the GPS. The simulation related parameters are listed in the Table 1 given below.

Parameter	Value
Network Field	100m * 100m
Number of Nodes	100
Initial energy	100J
Residual Energy threshold	25Jule
Sensing Radius	40.0 meter

The performance related parameters consists of two basic parameters, the energy related consumptions and the numbers of active nodes. The described methods is compared with the static clustering methods. This power saving scheme has increased the counts of active nodes in the specific network after a proximate number of iterations that compared to the static clustering methods without the sleeping schedule. The total energy related consumptions over time is also get reduced because the redundant data transmissions which are eliminated by the sleeping related procedure.

Figure below shows the number of active node plotted against the number of iterations. This values shows that there are much more nodes alive after a certain numbers of iterations than that of static methods. Next Figure shows the variations in total energy dissipations in the networking with respect to time frame.

Fig:2: Graphical representation of active nodes plotted against the iterations.

Fig: Overall energy dissipated plotted against the time

IV. CONCLUSION

An Clustering remains one of the most energy efficient data transmission and routing mechanism in particularly WSN. The aggregation of this particular data at the cluster heads get reduces its number of dataset transmissions and hence some saves a lot of energy requirements as before. The method described in this research initiation achieves very efficient clustering methodology with proper selection of (CH). The routing nodes selection is ultimately based on the residual energy which eventually makes the routing procedure energy efficient and relevant. The nodes consume minute amount of power during sleep periods and hence the lifetime of the entire network is get enhanced. If the nodes are liable to move to new clustering Heads when they are isolated due to any exhausted heads then the lifetime can again be increased. This can be implemented as an extension or future perspective to this research initiation.

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